

Extraction of matooke genotypes with superior quality traits from the breeding populations, using the RTBfoods SOPs

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Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this document, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes.

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ACRONYMS

EET	Early Evaluation Trials
IITA	International Institute of Tropical Agriculture
JAR	Just About Right
NARL	National Agricultural Research Laboratories
NARO	National Agricultural Research Organisation
RTB	Root, Tubers and Bananas
SOP	Standard Operating Procedures
TPA	Textural Profile Analysis
QDA	Quantitative Descriptive Analysis
WP	Work package

ABSTRACT

Accurate selection of *matooke* (East African Highland banana, *Musa spp.*) hybrids with end-user quality traits is essential for the development of improved cultivars. This report presents results of a study whose aim was to deploy colour and texture screening SOPs developed during Phase 1 of the RTBFoods project to extract hybrids with end-user acceptable colour and texture from an existing breeding population. Thirty-six *matooke* genotypes were screened using SOPs. The genotypes included twenty one hybrids and 15 landrace genotypes. A combination of sensory evaluations (Quantitative descriptive analysis) and instrumental analyses (TPA and Chroma meter) were employed to screen the genotypes. Statistical tools (XLSTAT) were used to identify genotypes with consistently desirable attributes.

Results of quantitative descriptive sensory analysis and texture profile analysis showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among the different *matooke* genotypes. The instrumentally and sensorially assessed colour and texture parameters of most *matooke* hybrid were outside the acceptability thresholds, implying that they would not be selected for advancement. However the instrumental and sensory parameters of *matooke* hybrid NARITA 17 and NAROBAN 4 were not significantly different from that of most local genotypes ($p > 0.05$). The sensory yellowness and colour homogeneity of hybrid NARITA17 and NAROBAN were close to that of Mbwazirume, one of the most preferred landrace genotype qualifying them for selection for advancement in the breeding pipeline and eventual variety release. Both NAROBAN 4 and NARITA 17 have been released to farming communities, confirming the usefulness of the SOPs to pick genotypes that satisfy consumer preference.

The use of the SOPs is being mainstreamed into the selection process of *matooke* breeding programme in NARO as medium throughput tools.

Keywords: *Matooke, Hybrids, Quality traits, Threshold, QDA, Colour, Texture, TPA, Chroma meter*

1. INTRODUCTION

The work presented in this report covers activities conducted under RTB breeding for quality, a project component that proceeded RTBFoods work packages 1 (WP1) and 2 (WP2).

The adoption of matooke hybrids remain extremely low (Madalla et al., 2023), mainly due to poor food quality characteristics. For this reason, the matooke breeders have recently included culinary attributes among the main criteria for selection of hybrids. Screening of matooke breeding populations to identify genotypes that combine resistance, high yields and culinary qualities has for long been constrained by lack of tools to screen for food quality. Breeders have been using sensory panels to screen hybrids. However, the large numbers involved, the lengthy matooke cooking process, human and financial resources involved remain a challenge (Meilgaard et al., 2007).

High throughput instrumental methods which can be used to assess a large number of samples in a short time could facilitate the screening process if they are correlated with the human assessment of sensory attributes that are linked with end-user preferences. Texture (specifically, the perceived softness and mouthfeel) and colour (yellowness of matooke and homogeneity) are key sensory attributes that influence consumer acceptance of steamed matooke (Khakasa et al. 2023).

In the last five years, the RTBFoods project identified and characterized key traits that drive preference and developed SOPs to measure them (Marimo et al. 2019, Nowakunda et al. 2019; Akankwasa et al., 2022, Nowakunda et al. 2023). The SOPs, generated under WP1 and WP2 included a matooke product profile (useful protocols for sensory analysis), Consumer tests, quantitative descriptive sensory analysis), texture and colour analysis.

In this study, we used the standard operating protocols (SOPs) developed in the RTBFoods project to screen matooke breeding populations.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Genotype screened

Matooke hybrids were harvested at green mature stage from the breeding fields at NARL-Kawanda and IITA-Uganda-Ssendusu stations and transported to the Food Science laboratory at NARL Kawanda. So far, 36 genotypes including twenty four hybrids in advanced trials (298220s-4, 17914S-24, 29586S-4, NRBN 4, M9, N13, M23, M33, N4, N7, N14, N8, N11, N12, N13, N23, N17, N18, N2, N16, N6, N19, N21, N24), four landrace genotypes used as females parents in the breeding scheme (Kaburagye, Kazirakwe, Nakawere, Enzirabahima), six commonly grown landraces (Nandigobe, Kisansa, Nfuuka, Nakyinyika, Musakala, Muvubo, Mpologoma), two the landraces commonly used as local checks (Nakitembe and Mbwazirume), and one of the most liked landrace (Kibuzi).

2.2. Sensory analysis

The green mature cooking bananas were peeled, wrapped in banana leaves, and steamed under the same cooking conditions (Marimo et al., 2021) in two separate big saucepans as separate bundles marked with distinct colour strings to ease identification.

Quantitative descriptive sensory evaluation was performed with a 12-member trained panel at the Food Biosciences Laboratories, NARL-Kawanda to establish the intensity of the sensory quality of the different matooke genotypes under evaluation. Matooke samples for quantitative descriptive sensory analysis were prepared following established standard operating procedures (SOP) (Nowakunda et al., 2019). The sensory parameters assessed were: softness by touch, mouthfeel, taste, moldability, smell, texture, attractiveness, hardness by touch and appearance. Samples were evaluated and scored against the developed descriptors. The appearance of matooke was described by colour and homogeneity of the colour, while the texture was described by firmness, moistness and smoothness all measured by mouth, while hardness and moldability were by touch. One sample was served at a time on disposable plates and presented with a glass of water for rinsing their mouths (Nowakunda et al., 2019).

2.3. Instrumental analysis of texture and colour

Portions of the same samples were transported to the laboratory for analyzing the quantitative indicators for instrumental analyses. The texture of each sample portion was analyzed using a TMS-Pilot texture analyzer following a texture profile analysis (TPA) procedure (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00602>). For colour, the cooked matooke colour was determined according to Khakasa et al., 2024 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foohum.2024.100268>). A Konica Minolta chroma metre, CR-400 was used to measure colour intensity of cooked matooke in terms of lightness (L^*), greenness (a^*), and yellowness (b^*).

2.4. Statistical Analysis

Data analysis of the sensory and instrumental data was performed using XLSTAT (Addinsoft 2023).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Assessment of the textural traits of the matooke genotypes

Results of quantitative descriptive sensory analysis and textural profiles analysis of the 36 matooke genotypes are presented in Table 1. The results show significant differences among the different matooke genotypes. Some of the genotypes were scored above the QDA thresholds (Table 2) while others were scored below for all the QDA sensory parameters. Yet, some genotypes have both traits below or above QDA thresholds. Generally, the landrace genotypes scores (Table 1) were closer to the intensity thresholds for 60-70% of consumers (Table 2).

Hybrid genotypes N6 and N2 had high intensity scores for firmness in mouth at 7.38 and N2 7.25 respectively while landrace genotype Nakitembe had the lowest at 1.9. Both hybrid's textural parameters was outside the acceptability threshold range (Table 2) and fell in the category of 'bad' genotypes. Also, a hybrid NAROBAN 4 was among the lowest at 1.50. Nakitembe is one of the most preferred local genotypes while NAROBAN 4 is a released

hybrid. Acceptability threshold for firmness was found to be between 2.3-2.8 (Table 2). Genotypes that fall far outside this range would, therefore not be described as 'Good' by consumers.

Matooke hybrid genotype N21 was described as having the highest intensity score for stickiness at 7.6 the stickiest while another hybrid N2 had the least score at 2.88. Stickiness is related to how much the mashed matooke holds together.

With respect to hardness assessed instrumentally (TPA), hybrids were among the hardest but also among the softest. For example, hybrid N6 was the hardest at 8.66N while again hybrid N21 was the least 'hard' at 1.34 (Table1). It is important to note that whereas consumers prefer 'soft' genotypes; too soft genotypes are also often rejected. Consumers describe such genotypes as '*watery*'. Acceptability threshold for hardness (TPA) was found to be between 2.0-2.6 (Table 2).

Cohesiveness, another TPA parameter, which measures how well the sample holds together after deformation revealed that hybrids N17 was the most cohesive at 1.62 while 29586S-4 another hybrid was least cohesive at 0.02. Hybrid N19 and Kabucuragye, a landrace used as a female parent in the breeding scheme had negative values at -1.37 and -1.72 respectively.

Table 1: Means of QDA and Instrumental (TPA) textural parameters

Variables	Firmness M	Moisture M	TPA							
			Smoothness M	hardness T	Moldability T	Stickiness T	Hardness (N)	Cohesiveness	Adhesiveness	
29820S-4	6.57 ^{abc}	3.57 ^{h-j}	8.14 ^{a-e}	5.71 ^{b-d}	8.14 ^{a-d}	5.71 ^{b-e}	5.74 ^{b-f}	0.63 ^{b-e}	-	0.94 ^{a-f}
17914S-24	7.63 ^a	2.13 ^j	8.25 ^{a-e}	5.88 ^{bc}	8.2 ^{a-d}	5.88 ^{a-e}	1.47 ^{kl}	0.42 ^{b-f}	-	0.25 ^a
N8	2.66 ^{h-k}	6.47 ^{a-d}	8.00 ^{a-e}	2.91 ^{f-j}	8.81 ^{ab}	7.31 ^{ab}	4.01 ^{e-k}	0.47 ^{b-f}	-	0.73 ^{a-f}
NKWR	4.6 ^{c-h}	5.81 ^{b-e}	8.01 ^{a-e}	4.18 ^{c-g}	8.36 ^{a-c}	5.52 ^{b-e}	4.33 ^{e-i}	0.60 ^{b-e}	-	2.18 ^g
ENZ	3.0 ^{g-k}	7.57 ^{ab}	7.14 ^{b-k}	2.71 ^{f-j}	8.29 ^{a-d}	6.43 ^{a-d}	4.24 ^{e-j}	0.53 ^{b-f}	-	0.79 ^{a-f}
NKT	1.94 ^{jk}	7.33 ^{a-c}	8.68 ^{ab}	1.87 ^{ij}	8.04 ^{a-d}	6.79 ^{a-c}	3.50 ^{f-l}	0.43 ^{b-f}	-	0.61 ^{a-e}
N21	2.45 ^{i-k}	6.60 ^{a-d}	8.45 ^{a-c}	2.40 ^{g-j}	8.35 ^{a-c}	7.60 ^a	1.34 ^l	0.87 ^b	-	1.26 ^{a-g}
N24	4.45 ^{c-i}	6.15 ^{b-e}	6.15 ^{g-k}	4.45 ^{c-f}	6.55 ^{c-f}	5.50 ^{b-f}	2.22 ^{i-l}	0.51 ^{b-f}	-	0.30 ^{ab}
MUV	3.56 ^{f-k}	7.25 ^{a-c}	7.56 ^{a-g}	2.88 ^{f-j}	8.44 ^{a-c}	4.69 ^{d-h}	3.01 ^{g-l}	0.48 ^{b-f}	-	0.47 ^{a-d}
MPO	4.0 ^{e-j}	6.00 ^{b-e}	8.75 ^{ab}	2.75 ^{f-j}	7.25 ^{a-f}	6.75 ^{a-c}	4.75 ^{d-i}	0.46 ^{b-f}	-	1.34 ^{b-g}
29586S-4	6.5 ^{a-d}	4.83 ^{d-i}	7.83 ^{a-g}	4.17 ^{c-g}	7.83 ^{a-e}	4.17 ^{e-h}	7.39 ^{a-c}	0.02 ^f	-	0.52 ^{a-e}
KIS	3.76 ^{f-k}	5.74 ^{b-f}	8.66 ^{ab}	3.50 ^{e-i}	8.43 ^{a-c}	5.66 ^{b-e}	5.38 ^{b-g}	0.37 ^{b-f}	-	1.48 ^{d-g}
N17	3.88 ^{e-j}	6.55 ^{a-d}	6.55 ^{d-k}	3.75 ^{d-i}	6.54 ^{c-f}	4.81 ^{d-g}	2.70 ^{h-l}	1.62 ^a	-	0.57 ^{a-e}
N15	5.86 ^{a-f}	4.49 ^{e-i}	4.53 ^{lm}	6.68 ^{ab}	3.88 ^g	3.60 ^{f-h}	7.64 ^{ab}	0.51 ^{b-f}	-	0.41 ^{a-c}
N6	7.38 ^a	4.00 ^{f-i}	2.63 ⁿ	8.00 ^a	2.50 ^g	3.50 ^{gh}	8.66 ^a	0.52 ^{b-f}	-	0.65 ^{a-e}
MBW	3.8 ^{e-k}	6.48 ^{a-d}	7.80 ^{a-g}	3.83 ^{d-i}	7.89 ^{a-e}	5.54 ^{b-e}	4.70 ^{d-i}	0.42 ^{b-f}	-	1.49 ^{d-g}
NKYK	4.05 ^{e-j}	5.59 ^{c-f}	7.81 ^{a-g}	4.19 ^{c-g}	8.06 ^{a-d}	5.48 ^{b-f}	4.94 ^{c-h}	0.27 ^{c-f}	-	1.23 ^{a-g}
NAND	1.92 ^{jk}	8.15 ^a	9.08 ^a	2.08 ^{h-j}	8.23 ^{a-d}	6.77 ^{a-c}	2.50 ^{h-l}	0.30 ^{b-f}	-	0.90 ^{a-f}
N11	6.37 ^{a-d}	7.28 ^{a-c}	3.88 ^{mn}	7.00 ^{ab}	5.88 ^f	4.47 ^{e-h}	1.69 ^{j-l}	0.46 ^{b-f}	-	0.36 ^{a-c}
Kibuzi	3.44 ^{g-k}	6.14 ^{b-e}	7.20 ^{b-j}	3.65 ^{e-i}	8.43 ^{a-c}	5.06 ^{c-g}	3.83 ^{f-l}	0.45 ^{b-f}	-	0.95 ^{a-f}
NFK	4.23 ^{d-j}	5.27 ^{d-h}	7.46 ^{a-h}	4.07 ^{c-h}	7.89 ^{a-e}	5.16 ^{c-g}	3.17 ^{f-l}	0.49 ^{b-f}	-	0.85 ^{a-f}
N2	7.25 ^{ab}	3.25 ^{ij}	3.63 ^{mn}	7.75 ^a	2.50 ^g	2.88 ^h	4.43 ^{e-i}	0.55 ^{b-f}	-	0.37 ^{a-c}
KAB	5.10 ^{b-g}	6.01 ^{b-e}	5.82 ^{h-l}	4.56 ^{c-f}	7.16 ^{a-e}	5.30 ^{c-g}	3.01 ^{g-l}	0.73 ^{b-d}	-	1.72 ^{fg}
MUS	3.20 ^{g-k}	5.81 ^{b-e}	7.91 ^{a-f}	3.06 ^{f-j}	8.07 ^{a-d}	5.62 ^{b-e}	4.66 ^{d-i}	0.44 ^{b-f}	-	1.47 ^{d-g}
N4	4.29 ^{d-j}	6.17 ^{b-e}	5.52 ^{kl}	4.71 ^{c-f}	6.07 ^{ef}	4.71 ^{d-h}	3.13 ^{f-l}	0.39 ^{b-d}	-	0.35 ^{a-c}

N14	4.33 ^{c-i}	6.00 ^{b-e}	6.22 ^{f-k}	4.11 ^{c-g}	6.94 ^{b-f}	4.67 ^{d-h}	3.50 ^{f-l}	0.51 ^{b-f}	-	0.91 ^{a-f}
N19	4.04 ^{e-j}	6.04 ^{b-e}	6.50 ^{e-k}	3.83 ^{d-i}	6.38 ^{d-f}	6.42 ^{a-d}	7.05 ^{a-d}	0.08 ^{ef}	-	1.37 ^{c-g}
KAZ	3.05 ^{g-k}	6.48 ^{a-d}	7.80 ^{a-g}	2.85 ^{f-j}	7.89 ^{a-e}	5.54 ^{b-e}	4.73 ^{d-i}	0.40 ^{b-f}	-	1.57 ^{e-g}
M33	3.23 ^{g-k}	6.12 ^{b-e}	6.45 ^{e-k}	3.15 ^{f-j}	7.26 ^{a-f}	4.75 ^{d-g}	4.95 ^{c-h}	0.40 ^{b-f}	-	0.66 ^{a-e}
N23	4.75 ^{c-i}	3.75 ^{g-j}	6.50 ^{e-k}	5.67 ^{b-d}	6.50 ^{c-f}	4.75 ^{d-g}	7.00 ^{a-d}	0.25 ^{c-f}	-	0.92 ^{a-f}
N13	3.16 ^{g-k}	6.09 ^{b-e}	7.13 ^{b-k}	3.47 ^{e-j}	8.44 ^{a-c}	5.33 ^{c-g}	3.88 ^{e-l}	0.15 ^{ef}	-	1.19 ^{a-g}
M9	2.5 ^{i-k}	5.96 ^{b-e}	6.88 ^{c-k}	3.00 ^{f-j}	7.58 ^{a-f}	4.25 ^{e-h}	4.83 ^{d-i}	0.49 ^{b-f}	-	0.72 ^{a-f}
N7	6.1 ^{a-e}	5.50 ^{c-f}	5.75 ^{i-l}	5.40 ^{b-e}	6.10 ^{ef}	4.75 ^{d-g}	2.41 ^{h-l}	0.82 ^{bc}	-	1.37 ^{c-g}
N18	3.84 ^{e-j}	5.31 ^{d-g}	7.25 ^{b-i}	3.95 ^{c-h}	8.02 ^{a-d}	3.98 ^{e-f}	6.44 ^{a-e}	0.16 ^{d-f}	-	1.20 ^{a-g}
NAROBN 4	1.50 ^k	7.25 ^{a-c}	7.75 ^{a-g}	1.50 ^j	9.00 ^a	4.00 ^{e-h}	3.00 ^{g-l}	0.30 ^{b-f}	-	0.90 ^{a-f}
N12	3.13 ^{g-k}	6.21 ^{b-e}	5.54 ^{ijkl}	3.63 ^{e-i}	6.54 ^{c-f}	7.54 ^a	3.54 ^{f-l}	0.18 ^{d-f}	-	1.21 ^{a-g}
Pr >										
F(Model)	<0.00	<0.00	<0.00	<0.00	<0.00	<0.00	<0.00	<0.00	<0.00	<0.00
Significant	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Numbers with the same superscript letters in each column are not significantly different ($p>0.05$)

Landrace abbreviations in the table: KAB = Kabucuragye, NFK = Nfuuka, MPO = Mpologoma, NKT = Nakitembe, ENZ = Enzirabahima, KAZ = Kazirakwe, KIS = Kisansa, MBW = Mbwazirume, NAND = Nandogobe, MUS -Musakala, NAKWR = Nakawere, NKYY = Nakinyika, MUV = Muvubo, KBZ = Kibuzi, N = NARITA and those with numerals are all hybrids.

Table 2: Sensory and Instrumental thresholds for some colour and textural attributes

Colour					
		QDA	Instrumental		
Mean liking (all attributes)	6.077	yellowness	colour (b)	QDA homogeneity	
Mean liking by consumers/mean scores		5.761	25.88	6.061	
Threshold acceptability at JAR 60%		6.6	27.7		
Threshold acceptability at JAR 70%		8.3	29.3		
Threshold range		6.6 ≥8.3	≥29.3		
Texture					
Mean firmness (M)	2.21				
Mean hardness (T)	2.37				
Mean Cohesiveness	0.711				
Texture		firmness (QDA)	Hardness (T)	Cohesiveness	Hardness (INST)
Threshold in terms of JAR softness (60%)		2.3	2.5		2.00
Threshold in terms of JAR softness (70%)		2.8	2.00		≤2
Threshold in terms of JAR mouthfeel (60%)		3.2	2.5	0.58	2.6
Threshold in terms of JAR mouthfeel (70%)		1.9	1.8	0.85	≤2.6

INST=Instrumental, M = in mouth, T = in hand

3.2. Relationships between QDA and TPA textural parameters of the matooke genotypes

Principal Component Analysis biplot (Figure 1) shows the relationships between textural parameters (QDA and TPA) of the 33 matooke genotypes. The figure shows that the first two principal components (F1 and F2), explain 66.57% of the total variance. The largest proportion of the variance is captured by F1 (49.88%), which makes it the most important axis in explaining data variation. Although F2 (16.69%) explains a smaller portion of the variance, it is equally important because it still contributes to separating observations. Most of the matooke genotypes clustered around the centre, signifying a lack of strong separation along the principal components. Matooke hybrids N2, N6, and N15, were farther along the positive F1 axis, suggesting they have high values for hardness by touch (T), Firmness in the mouth (M), and TPA hardness.

Figure 1: PCA plot of QDA and TPA parameters with the 33 matooke genotypes

Firmness in the mouth (M), hardness by touch (T), and TPA hardness of most genotypes were strongly associated with positive F1, indicating their significant contribution to the principal component. The cohesiveness of matooke hybrids N17 and N21 was spread along the F2 axis, signifying variability in cohesiveness and moistness in the mouth (M). Cohesiveness and adhesiveness contribute more along F2, differentiating samples along this axis. Moistness in the mouth (M) and moldability by touch (T) were negatively correlated with firmness-related attributes, suggesting that higher moistness is associated with lower firmness. The hybrids N21 and N17 were associated with high moistness in the mouth (M), smoothness in the mouth, and

moldability by touch (T). This implies that these clones when cooked tend to be softer, more moldable, and smoother. To be preferred however, these parameters should fall within acceptability thresholds.

3.3. Assessment of the textural traits of the matooke genotypes

Results of instrumental colour analysis (chroma) and the mean quantitative descriptive sensory analysis (QDA) of cooked samples of the 36 matooke genotypes are presented in Table 3. The results showed significant differences among the 36 genotypes screened. The key parameters included; the QDA overall yellowness of the cooked matooke; homogeneity of colour (evenness in colour distribution); instrumental lightness (L^*) of the raw and cooked pulp (L-rawpulp and L-cookedpulp respectively), the yellowness (b^*) of the raw and cooked pulp (b -rawpulp and b -cooked pulp respectively (Table 3)

Landrace genotypes Nakitembe, Enzirabahima, Kazirakwe and Nandigobe had the highest QDA intensity scores for yellowness at 8.83, 8.57, 8.67 and 8.54 respectively. Genotypes with lowest yellowness intensity scores were hybrids N8, N23 and N21 at 2.00, 2.17 and 1.10 respectively. Acceptability thresholds for yellowness were found to be between 6.6 and 8.3 (Table 2) signifying that the yellowness of these hybrids might not be appealing to consumers.

Landrace genotype Enzirabahima, Nakitembe, and hybrid N17 had the highest intensity scores for homogeneity of colour at 9.29, 8.80 and 8.76 respectively. Hybrids N23, N13, and N8 had the lowest intensity score at 3.7, 3.12 and 3.0 respectively against the acceptability threshold average of 6.0. These observations are consistent with previous studies (Marimo et al. 2019, Akankwasa et al. 2020) which identified the landrace genotypes to have superior quality attributes. However, some hybrids like N17 were closer to the landrace genotypes.

Regarding the instrumental colour parameter, the Lightness (L^* Values) in raw and cooked matooke samples, the highest L^* raw and cooked pulp values were observed in hybrid genotype N18 (64.94 and 50.14), landrace genotype Kibuzi (63.38 and 50.11), and hybrid N14 (63.65 and 53.15) (Table 3). This, suggests that when raw, the pulps of these genotypes have lighter-coloured raw pulps, which reduces after cooking.

For the yellowness (b^* Values) in raw and cooked matooke, the highest values (most yellow) were in observed in Kabucuragye (34.19) and Mbwazirume (31.79). Others were N17 (30.10 and 27.65), Nakyetengu (29.80 and 28.5), and N23 (29.90 and 18.90). Matooke hybrids N18 (13.68) and N15 (16.30) had the lowest cooked b^* values, meaning they might not have a strong yellow appearance after cooking. It is important to note that the yellowness of landrace genotypes increases after cooking while most hybrids' yellowness reduces after cooking (Table 3).

Table 3: Means of QDA and instrumental Colour Parameters

Variables	Yellow	Homogeneity of colour	L*rawpulp	b*rawpulp	L*cooked	b*cooked
KAB	8.39 ^{a-d}	7.79 ^{a-d}	62.09 ^{ab}	25.48 ^{b-f}	55.22 ^{ab}	34.19 ^a
MPO	8.25 ^{a-e}	8.00 ^{a-d}	63.07 ^{ab}	26.96 ^{a-d}	52.20 ^{a-e}	29.76 ^{a-d}
NKT	8.83 ^a	8.80 ^{ab}	60.95 ^{a-c}	27.20 ^{a-d}	51.68 ^{a-f}	30.38 ^{a-c}
ENZ	8.57 ^{a-c}	9.29 ^a	62.02 ^{ab}	23.96 ^{d-h}	53.78 ^{a-d}	29.27 ^{a-d}
N17	7.94 ^{a-f}	8.76 ^{ab}	61.50 ^{a-c}	30.10 ^a	52.65 ^{a-e}	27.65 ^{a-f}
KAZ	8.67 ^{ab}	8.21 ^{a-c}	62.14 ^{ab}	25.73 ^{b-e}	51.15 ^{a-g}	28.64 ^{a-d}
KIS	7.29 ^{a-h}	7.45 ^{a-e}	63.58 ^{ab}	24.50 ^{c-g}	54.13 ^{a-c}	27.78 ^{a-f}
N14	6.33 ^{d-i}	7.72 ^{a-d}	63.65 ^{ab}	28.30 ^{ab}	53.15 ^{a-e}	21.85 ^{e-j}
MBW	8.17 ^{a-e}	8.21 ^{a-c}	60.27 ^{a-c}	26.14 ^{b-e}	50.85 ^{a-g}	31.79 ^{ab}
NAND	8.54 ^{a-c}	7.62 ^{a-e}	60.00 ^{a-c}	25.00 ^{c-f}	53.89 ^{a-c}	28.87 ^{a-d}
N7	7.95 ^{a-f}	7.90 ^{a-d}	61.45 ^{a-c}	29.70 ^a	47.26 ^{e-h}	28.35 ^{a-e}
NAROBAN 4	7.25 ^{a-h}	6.50 ^{c-e}	63.00 ^{ab}	24.32 ^{c-g}	54.87 ^{ab}	27.45 ^{b-f}
MUS	7.69 ^{a-g}	7.59 ^{a-e}	61.61 ^{a-c}	21.62 ^{g-i}	52.34 ^{a-e}	29.40 ^{a-d}
MUV	6.75 ^{a-i}	7.39 ^{b-e}	60.05 ^{a-c}	26.19 ^{b-e}	52.93 ^{a-e}	29.50 ^{a-d}
N4	5.93 ^{f-i}	7.60 ^{a-e}	62.08 ^{ab}	27.61 ^{a-c}	52.63 ^{a-e}	24.72 ^{c-i}
NKYK	7.45 ^{a-h}	7.73 ^{a-d}	60.60 ^{a-c}	29.80 ^a	45.32 ^{gh}	28.50 ^{a-e}
NAKWR	7.89 ^{a-f}	8.28 ^{a-c}	45.43 ^d	27.60 ^{a-c}	45.30 ^{gh}	25.44 ^{b-h}
N24	6.65 ^{b-i}	8.20 ^{a-c}	58.95 ^{bc}	26.85 ^{a-d}	51.95 ^{a-e}	21.55 ^{f-k}
KBZ	6.42 ^{d-i}	6.94 ^{b-e}	63.38 ^{ab}	23.33 ^{e-i}	50.11 ^{b-g}	26.11 ^{b-g}
N2	5.75 ^{g-i}	6.38 ^{c-e}	62.30 ^{ab}	29.63 ^a	47.99 ^{c-g}	24.94 ^{c-i}
N11	6.21 ^{e-i}	7.50 ^{a-e}	60.47 ^{a-c}	23.41 ^{e-i}	56.78 ^a	21.19 ^{f-k}

NFK	6.65 ^{b-i}	7.10 ^{b-e}	59.07 ^{bc}	23.79 ^{d-h}	53.32 ^{a-e}	24.85 ^{c-i}
N15	5.16 ^{ij}	6.76 ^{c-e}	61.58 ^{a-c}	28.08 ^{ab}	51.69 ^{a-f}	16.30 ^{j-l}
N23	2.17 ^{kl}	3.67 ^f	60.60 ^{a-c}	29.90 ^a	51.15 ^{a-g}	18.90 ^{h-l}
N18	4.85 ^{ij}	6.91 ^{b-e}	64.94 ^a	17.48 ^k	50.41 ^{a-g}	13.68 ^l
N19	6.67 ^{b-i}	5.75 ^e	60.86 ^{a-c}	20.93 ^{h-j}	51.04 ^{a-g}	19.32 ^{h-l}
N12	4.96 ^{ij}	6.25 ^{de}	62.26 ^{ab}	23.13 ^{e-i}	48.32 ^{c-g}	19.64 ^{g-l}
N21	1.10 ^l	1.85 ^g	58.45 ^{bc}	27.00 ^{a-d}	51.10 ^{a-g}	24.05 ^{c-i}
M33	6.29 ^{d-i}	6.78 ^{c-e}	56.54 ^c	20.47 ^{ij}	48.82 ^{b-g}	24.32 ^{c-i}
N6	5.50 ^{hi}	6.13 ^{de}	41.40 ^d	24.60 ^{c-g}	49.00 ^{b-g}	23.30 ^{d-i}
M9	6.50 ^{c-i}	6.50 ^{c-e}	60.09 ^{a-c}	18.22 ^{jk}	47.36 ^{d-h}	15.29 ^{kl}
N13	3.56 ^{jk}	3.12 ^{fg}	61.14 ^{a-c}	22.13 ^{f-i}	45.35 ^{f-h}	18.66 ^{i-l}
N8	2.00 ^{kl}	3.00 ^{fg}	62.41 ^{ab}	16.21 ^k	41.91 ^h	15.74 ^{j-l}
Pr >						
F(Model)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Significant	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Numbers with the same superscript in each column are not significantly different ($p > 0.05$)

Landrace abbreviations in the table: KAB = Kabucuragye, NFK = Nfuuka, MPO = Mpologoma, NKT = Nakitembe, ENZ = Enzirabahima, KAZ = Kazirakwe, KIS = Kisansa, MBW = Mbwazirume, NAND = Nandogobe, MUS = Musakala, NAKWR = Nakawere, NKYY = Nakinyika, MUV = Muvubo, KBZ = Kibuzi, N = NARITA and those with numerals are all hybrids.

3.4. Relationships between QDA and instrumental colour parameters of the matooke genotypes

The PCA plot (Figure 2) shows the relationship between QDA colour and chroma parameters of the 36 raw and cooked matooke genotypes. The figure shows that axes F1 and F2 explain 67.98% of the total variation in the data, which means that they capture most of the significant differences between the matooke varieties.

The L* values (L*-pulp and L*-cooked) are positioned toward the upper right. L* represents lightness, indicating that samples in this direction are lighter in colour. The b values (b*-pulp and b*-cooked) and homogeneity of colour also clustered on the right side of the PCA plot. The b* value represents the yellowness of the sample, thus, samples in this area would be more yellow. Homogeneity of colour means the evenness of colour distribution, meaning samples in this direction have a more uniform appearance.

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